

Combining ability analysis on restorability for cytoplasmic male sterility in hybrid rice

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Restorability, estimated as the mean spikelet fertility or seed set percentage in the F₁ generation, refers to the potential of a certain cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line to restore fertility in the hybrid derived from it. It is caused by nuclear gene(s) of the restorer (R) lines, and nuclear (N) and cytoplasmic (C) background of the CMS (A) line, as well as the interaction between the two. To understand the relative importance of each factor, three series of iso-nuclear lines with three types of CMS backgrounds (nine CMS lines) were developed. Then we produced 72 combinations according to North Carolina Design II (9 CMS lines, 8 restorers). In the summer of 1994, each combination was grown in two rows with 9 plants each at 33.3- × 20-cm spacing. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications in which the main factor was the restorers. Data on seed set percentage were collected from the center five plants of either row. Statistical analysis was based on the sin⁻¹√p transformation data.

General combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) values^a for restorability for CMS.

CMS line nuclear background	Restorers								GCA	SE
	6323	72922	Ce-64	Hui-403	HR195	Hui-552	CDR22	Minghui-63 (check)		
N-Qing	1.49*	-0.90	-1.02	-1.74**	-0.84	0.61	0.78	1.62*	1.80**	
N-17	-0.18	-0.56	0.11	-0.14	-0.33	1.38*	-0.61	0.34	-0.41	
N-Shan (check)	-1.30*	1.45*	0.91	1.88**	1.18	-1.98**	0.17	-1.96**	-1.39**	
GCA	-4.25**	1.44	0.03	2.00*	3.70**	-4.55**	2.08*	-0.46		0.232
SE									0.72	0.614

^a*, ** = significance at 0.05 and 0.01 level, respectively.

Variance analysis revealed that effects on restorability were significantly different among restorers, CMS line nuclear backgrounds, and N-R interactions, while not significantly different among the cytoplasmic background of CMS lines, C-R interactions, C-N interactions, and C-N-R interactions.

Subsequent analysis of combining ability showed that HR195 and N-Qing had the highest general combining ability (GCA) among restorers and N-Qing among nuclear background of CMS lines. Among the restorers, the GCA for restorability of CDR22, Hui-403, 72922, and Ce-64 was higher than that of Minghui-63, a widely used restorer in hybrid rice production, and the GCA of 6323 and Hui-552 was lower. Both N-Qing and N-17 showed higher GCA

for restorability than did N-Shan, a commonly used CMS line nuclear background in China (see table).

The relative importance analysis suggested that the restorer was ranked highest in restorability for CMS, followed by CMS line nuclear background, and N-R interaction. The GCA of the restorer and the nuclear background of the CMS line primarily determined the restorability for CMS (accounting for 86.4%), with specific combining ability (13.6%) having some influence.

Thus, to improve CMS restorability, emphasis must be placed on the selection of restorers and maintainers (the nuclear background of CMS lines) with higher GCA. HR195 and N-Qing have therefore been exploited in hybrid rice breeding for their higher GCA for CMS restorability. ■

Male sterile line in rice (*Oryza sativa*) developed with *O. glumaepatula* cytoplasm

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Most of the commercial hybrids of indica rice are based on the wild abortive (WA) source of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS). More than 95% of all hybrid rice grown in China is based on the WA cytoplasmic system. Such cytoplasmic uniformity of hybrid rice could lead to genetic vulnerability to diseases and insects. To overcome this problem, diversification of the source of CMS is essential.

We developed a CMS line with the cytoplasm of AA genome wild species

O. glumaepatula and the nuclear genome of IR64. Serving as female parents, 48 accessions of 3 wild species (AA genome) were crossed with IR64, one of the restorers of

WA cytoplasm. Data on pollen sterility were recorded in F₁ and backcross generations. Hybrids showing 70% or more pollen sterility were subsequently

Pollen fertility of F₁ and backcross progenies derived from the cross of *O. glumaepatula* (Acc 100969) and IR64.

Generation	Pollen fertility (% of progeny) ^a					Plants analyzed (no.)
	CS	S	PS	PF	F	
BC ₈	100	0	0	0	0	45
BC ₇	92	8	0	0	0	12
BC ₆	86	14	0	0	0	41
BC ₅	95	4	1	0	0	147
BC ₄	57	43	0	0	0	7
BC ₃	65	20	10	5	0	20
BC ₂	0	2	16	43	39	89
BC ₁	21	23	30	14	12	197
F ₁	17	83	0	0	0	6

^aPollen fertility classes: CS = completely sterile, 0% pollen fertility; S = sterile, 1-10% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 11.30% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 31.60% pollen fertility; F = fertile, 61.100% pollen fertility.